

Reproduction in Domestic Animals

Table of Contents Volume 54 · Supplement 3 · September 2019 · 1–150

EDITORIAL

K. PLEMYASHOV, E. NIKITKINA 3

SUPPLEMENT REVIEWS

T. SEELING, E. HAUCKE, A. NAVARRETE SANTOS, K. J. GRYBEL, J. GÜRKE, S. M. PENDZIALEK, M. SCHINDLER, A. SIMM, A. NAVARRETE SANTOS
Glyoxalase 1 expression is downregulated in preimplantation blastocysts of diabetic rabbits 4–11

C. OLIVIERO, S. JUNNIKALA, O. PELTONIEMI
The challenge of large litters on the immune system of the sow and the piglets 12–21

S. MEYERS, E. BULKELEY, A. FOUTOUHI
Sperm mitochondrial regulation in motility and fertility in horses 22–28

C. RITTER, A. BEAVER, M. A. G. VON KEYSERLINGK
The complex relationship between welfare and reproduction in cattle 29–37

S. CHEN, J. SCHOEN
Air-liquid interface cell culture: From airway epithelium to the female reproductive tract 38–45

SUPPLEMENT ARTICLES

J. ALPOIM-MOREIRA, C. FERNANDES, M. R. REBORDÃO, A. AMARAL, P. PINTO-BRAVO, M. BLIEBERNICHT, D. J. SKARZYNSKI, G. FERREIRA-DIAS
Collagens and DNA methyltransferases in mare endometrosis 46–52

B. C. PEREIRA, I. ORTIZ, J. M. DORADO, M. A. DIAZ-JIMENEZ, C. CONSUEGRA, J. GOSALVEZ, M. HIDALGO
Effect of permeable cryoprotectant-free vitrification on DNA fragmentation of equine oocyte cumulus cells 53–56

WORKSHOPS 57–62

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS 63–74

YOUNG SCIENTIST COMPETITION 75–78

POSTERS 79–149